

A STUDY ON THE CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN THE MODERN EDUCATION - SOCIOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE ON SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Purpose:

This study throws light on the problems faced by the students, parents, and educational institutions in learning and delivering modern education.

Methodology / Design /Approaches: This research is descriptive by nature by using secondary data analysis of the Sociological perspective on traditional and modern education. It is conducted to derive conclusion on sustainability of education system.-

Findings and results: it is found that there is relation in the teacher and student reliability overstay with decrease in social value system.

Originality/value: Application of sociological perspective on student learning and parents perspective on education to devise framework to make education sustainable.

Type of Paper: Secondary Research Analysis.

Keywords: education, modern, tradition, online education, Social, and Students.

INTRODUCTION

Modern Education is different from traditional education and the educational system taught in the schools and colleges presently is modern in nature. The relationship between school and college curriculum to prevailing needs and views of a society is important in considering sociological perspectives, and issues of accountability, and the responses are relevant and signifying to the curriculum of Modern education. The students are having online and offline classes. In the Modern education system, teachers are requiring updated skills. The present education system needs knowledge of using computers, and they have to plan for the education system technically. Teachers and Students are facing the problem of networks and other online teaching applications. Due to this reason, parents are facing financial problems. So that, they cannot satisfy their children’s basic technological needs. Education is socialization if children need to learn the norms, values, and skills needed to function in society and education is a primary vehicle for learning.

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Education is the social platform it integrates the society to work with people's common set of beliefs and values. Education is a social placement. It starts from grade school and students are identifying with the teacher's values, customs, and beliefs and this is the begging stage of learning. Because of modern education inequality are there in the educational system. Education helps in socializing, integration, placement, and cultural development of the people in the society. It also helps in eradicating social inequality. The various types of schools, institutes, colleges, and universities follow different innovative practices which will lead to educational inequalities in the present society. The Covid-19, Pandemic has brought a lot of changes in the delivery of education from traditional methods to Modern education. The socioeconomic background of the people affected education directly or indirectly. Because parents were not in a position to provide adequate learning resources which were their basic needs. Students faced many obstacles to cope with their learning than those who were in much more advanced situations and in well-funded schools.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the traditional education and the modern educational system.
- To understand the social perspective of the modern educational system.
- Challenges faced by Children, Parents, and Teachers.
- The remedial measures to reduce the gap in the education system.
- To understand the impact of Covid 19 pandemic challenges on the conventional education system.

CHANGING EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

1) Education Inequality:-

The conflict theories do not dispute most of the functions just described. It does give some of their different slants and talks about various ways in which education sustains social inequality. One of the examples involves the purpose of social placements. As most schools track their students starting in kinder garden, the students learn by their teachers in place of the first tracks. Slower students are placed in the slower tracks in high schools, three common tracks are the college track, vocational track, and general track.

The students help ensure bright learning as much as their abilities allow them. Slower students are not thought over their heads. Conflict theorist says that learning also helps social inequality on students' capability of their learning.

2) Traditional and Modern Education: -

Traditional and modern education are both related to each other and it different from each other. Earlier in history in our country, there was a time was no school. The children have accrued the education, and knowledge from their ancestors. At the time knowledge forcing only by the skills required for survival. The people who lived in the jungle got education from their ancestors taught how to hunt animals for their survival. They were taught about religious aspects. The kings send their sons to schools called in India “Gurukuls” At Gurukula they thought about how to use a weapon and how to protect themselves and how to attack their enemies. This school only belongs to the royal families. In coming years the importance of education is given to academic knowledge throughout the country. Schools were open for all students so that, they can come for learning. This was established in modern education after the time of science and technology were started. Due to the Covid pandemic, the education system is changed throughout the county. The

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government started a blended mode education system that is 40% of online classes and 60% of offline classes.

CHALLENGES OF MODERN EDUCATION IN SOCIOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES

1. Student’s Perspective: The students are facing many problems of modern education like they’re not adjusted to a new system that is online classes. They do not understand any subject knowledge as well as they cannot give more concentration in the online classes because of network problems which may be natural or technical. The students may not get accrue knowledge. The basic contact between teachers and students gap will be created because of the online education system. Sometimes students are not aware of the technical information regarding the uses of teaching websites.

2. Parents’ Perspective: The parents are not aware of the online classes. At this point, poor parents are not able to give good quality of education because they do not have a good financial background. They’re not able to give good quality mobile, laptops, and other data connectivity systems.

3. Teachers’ Perspective: Teachers do not have good contact with their students. At the same time, students do not listen to online classes. These all things happen during the Covid 19 pandemic. The students had online classes. Once they back to college they did not have any subject knowledge because of online classes.

THE CONSEQUENCE IN MODERN EDUCATION SOCIOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

The perspective focuses on social interaction in the classrooms, playgrounds, and school venues. The social interaction in schools affects the development of gender roles and the teacher’s expectation, and intellectual ability affects students. The major sociological perspective of education falls nicely into the functional, conflict, and symbolic interactions. The effect of the organization on education students, parents, and teachers are the main risk-taker of education because of the new education system socialization of the students the vary less in the society. Students are more attached to mobiles and other social networks, and due to this parents are not aware of which work their children are doing on the social network. Parents are not capable of providing resources for their children. The teachers are suffering from the lack of a network system and data has used the limitations per day. The equipment is not provided for the teachers in the institution.

SUGGESTION

From the social perspective modern education is good but when a new system is introduced awareness must give to the concerned people. Thus the education system should give the basic facilities for the required people. For those who are poor family background children for them, an alternative system can be provided.

CONCLUSION

Modern and Traditional Educational systems affect the students because of a lack of social Norms, Values, and Skills. During the Covid -19 pandemic the modern education growth are taken fastly. In this paper modern education how effect the sociologically to students, parents and teachers.

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